

Dissecting the Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test: An Item Response Theory analysis

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The author reports no conflicts of interest.

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This study presents a psychometric evaluation of the Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT7) based on item response theory. The participants ($N = 1204$) completed the CRT7 and provided self-reported information about their cognitive styles through the Preference for Intuition and Deliberation Scale (PID). A two-parameter logistic model was fitted to the data to obtain the item difficulty and discrimination parameters of the CRT7. The results showed that the items had good discriminatory power ($\alpha s = .80 - 2.92$), but the range of difficulty was restricted (βs ranged from $-.60$ to $.32$). Moreover, the CRT7 showed a pattern of correlations with the PID which was similar to that of the original CRT. When taken together, these results are evidence of the adequacy of the CRT7 as an expanded tool for measuring cognitive reflection; however, one of the newer items (the pig item) was consistently problematic across analyses, and so it is recommended that in future studies it should be removed from the CRT7.

Keywords: Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test, CRT7, item response theory, Preference for Intuition and Deliberation Scale, psychometric analysis

Introduction

Few methods have attracted as much attention in the psychology of reasoning and decision making as the Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT), which consists of three tricky items, including the notorious bat-and-ball problem (Frederick, 2005, p. 27):

A bat and a ball cost \$1.10 in total. The bat costs \$1.00 more than the ball. How much does the ball cost? _____ cents

This measure has been included in a vast number of recent studies and its widespread use helped direct researchers' attention toward the study of individual differences in rational reasoning and decision making (e.g. Toplak, West, & Stanovich, 2011), as well as in other domains (Baron, Scott, Fincher, & Emlen Metz, 2015; Pennycook, Fugelsang, & Koehler, 2015). Interestingly, despite its immense popularity, it is far

from clear what exactly the CRT measures. While it was originally intended to measure the ability to suppress compelling intuitive responses, it also shows moderate correlations with cognitive ability (Frederick, 2005; Toplak et al., 2011), and has been argued to reflect numeracy (Campitelli & Gerrans, 2014; Sinayev & Peters, 2015), as well as thinking dispositions such as analytical thinking (Pennycook & Ross, 2016) and/or reflectivity/impulsivity (Baron et al., 2015). Moreover, after the initial elation caused by the CRT had subsided, many researchers began to realise that there were other problems with this method that have to be dealt with in the present.

Current problems with the original Cognitive Reflection Test

One issue which has led to doubts about the validity of the CRT is that the general public is becoming increasingly familiar with it (Haigh, 2016). Many participants in recent studies have reported being familiar with at least one of the original problems and have produced more correct responses to the CRT than naive participants (Haigh, 2016; Pennycook, Cheyne, Koehler, & Fugelsang, 2015; Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016). Recently, however, Bialek and Pennycook (2017) have shown that similar patterns of correlations between the CRT and various outcome measures have been found among participants with previous exposure and participants without previous exposure to the test. They therefore conclude that familiarity with the CRT may not cause such a problem with validity as previously thought. Nevertheless, as participants may be exposed to the CRT through different sources (e.g. media, research, school) and with varying frequency, it is possible that familiarity with the test will become more of an issue in the future.

The second problem stems from the fact that there are only three items in the original test. As a consequence, the range of scores that can be obtained when using the CRT is limited, and there may be floor and ceiling effects. Awareness of this problem

has existed since the original article by Frederick (2005), which reported that on average 50% of people across different samples answered either none or all of the items correctly. Similar results have been obtained by other researchers (e.g. 55% in Bialek & Pennycook, 2017; 62% in Toplak et al., 2011). Also, some studies have reported unacceptably low reliability for the CRT, which likewise may be related to the small number of items in the test, but could also indicate that the items do not measure the same construct (Stuppel, Pitchford, Ball, Hunt, & Steel, 2017).

These issues could largely be resolved by designing new unfamiliar items that share the core characteristics of Frederick's (2005) test. Some research teams have already recognised this and have recently come up with new versions of the CRT (Primi, Morsanyi, Chiesi, Donati, & Hamilton, 2015; Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016; Toplak, West, & Stanovich, 2014). However, to ensure that the new versions are appropriate substitutes for the original test, they have to be carefully investigated from a psychometric standpoint. This was done recently by Primi et al. (2015) who applied an item response theory approach to developing and testing their new version of the test. Yet, to the best of my knowledge, no extensive item-level psychometric investigation of the remaining newly developed CRTs has been carried out. Therefore, in the present study I conduct an item response theory analysis of the seven-item Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT7) developed by Toplak et al. (2014).

Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test (CRT7)

Toplak et al. (2014) designed four new tricky problems that can either serve as substitute to the original CRT or can be added to it to produce a longer test.¹ They

¹ Keeping to the nomenclature used in Toplak et al. (2014) I refer to the three original items as the CRT3, the four new items as the CRT4, and the seven combined items as the CRT7.

showed that the CRT7 shares most of the important characteristics of the original three-item test: participants mainly produce either correct or intuitive incorrect responses to the new problems; it shows a similar pattern of correlations with thinking dispositions and cognitive ability, and, most importantly, it correlates with heuristics and biases tasks and predicts variance in them over and above cognitive abilities and thinking dispositions. In comparison with the original test, the CRT7 also shows better internal consistency ($\alpha = .72$ in Toplak et al., 2014) and, as the four new items are slightly easier than the original three, there is some reduction in floor effects². This led Toplak et al. (2014) to conclude that the CRT7 is an adequate extension to the original test and is ready for use in future research.

Since its development, the CRT7 has already been used in several studies, the results of which provide further evidence of its adequacy as an expanded measure of cognitive reflection. For example, it has been shown to correlate with several tasks from the decision making literature (Jackson, Kleitman, Howie, & Stankov, 2016) and to predict acceptance of unfair ultimatum games (Calvillo & Burgeno, 2015). While the CRT7 is gaining in popularity, we still have limited knowledge about its psychometric characteristics. The original study by Toplak et al. (2014) was based on a small sample of participants, and although they report some psychometric properties, such as reliability coefficients and inter-item correlations, others remain unknown. The latter include, for example, the dimensionality of the CRT7, and item-level characteristics

² Frederick (2005) does not report the reliability of the original CRT in his paper, but the Cronbach's alpha reported in previous studies has been found to be around $\alpha = .65$ (e.g. Bialek & Pennycook, 2017; Primi et al., 2015) and sometimes even considerably lower ($\alpha = .47$, Stuppel et al., 2017). As reported by Toplak et al. (2014), the mean probability of an item being correctly answered in the CRT4 (.24) is higher than in the CRT3 (.17).

such as discrimination and the difficulty of each problem. To address these limitations, I conducted a large-scale psychometric analysis of the CRT7 using item response theory.

Item response theory analysis

Item response theory (IRT) is a psychometric framework that has several advantages over the more commonly used classical test theory (CTT; Embretson & Reise, 2000; Hambleton, Swaminathan, & Rogers, 1991). It is based on linking the observed item responses to the latent person and item characteristics, and it has two core assumptions (Hambleton et al., 1991). Firstly, all examinees taking a test are expected to have a certain amount of latent ability or trait (symbolised by θ), which is assessed by the test and which can explain their performance on each item. This means that, at a given latent trait level, the examinee has a certain probability $P(\text{correct response} | \theta)$ of answering an item correctly, and the greater the person's ability is, the higher their chance of providing the correct answer to that item. Secondly, IRT states that the relationship between the examinee's performance and their item responses can be expressed through a logistic function called the item characteristic curve. While there are several IRT models which differ in the number of estimated item parameters (e.g. de Ayala, 2009), one of those most commonly used for items with a dichotomous response format is the two-parameter logistic model (2PL), in which the probability of a correct answer at a given latent trait level is expressed using the following equation (De Mars, 2010, p. 14):

$$P(\text{correct response} | \theta) = \frac{e^{1.7a_i(\theta - \beta_i)}}{1 + e^{1.7a_i(\theta - \beta_i)}}$$

As can be seen from the equation, the probability of answering an item correctly in the 2PL model at a given level of latent ability (θ) is a logistic function of two item parameters – *item difficulty* (symbolised by β) and *item discrimination* (symbolised by

α). Item difficulty, also sometimes called an item location parameter (de Ayala, 2009), is located on the same continuum as the respondent's latent ability (θ) and is equal to a level of latent trait that represents a 50% probability of the given item being answered correctly. The item discrimination parameter is defined as the slope of the item characteristic curve at its steepest point and it reflects how effectively an item discriminates between examinees with different levels of latent ability.

Figure 1 presents the item characteristic curves of two hypothetical items under the 2PL model. As can be seen from the figure the probability of a correct response to both items increases with higher levels of latent ability θ . However, it is obvious that the relationship between θ and the probability is not identical for the two presented problems, as the items differ in their difficulty and discrimination parameters. The difficulty of the two items is illustrated as the value of the x-axis at the point where the item characteristic curves intersect the horizontal line (item 1: $\beta = -1$; item 2: $\beta = 1$). Considering the differences in the difficulty of the two items, examinees who are one standard deviation below the average level of latent ability ($\theta = -1$) have a 50% probability of answering the first item correctly. However, they only have around a 5% probability of giving a correct answer to the second, more difficult item. The other way in which the two item characteristic curves differ is in their steepness, which is a graphical representation of the item's discriminatory power. The item characteristic curve of item 1 ($\alpha = 1.8$), which is more discriminating, is steeper, indicating that the same difference in a participant's latent ability results in a larger change in the probability of a correct response to this item, than for item 2 ($\alpha = 1$), which is less discriminating.

Figure 1. Item characteristic curves of two hypothetical items under the two-parameter logistic model. Item difficulty (β 's) is indicated by the values of the x-axis at the point where the item curves intersect the horizontal line (item 1: $\beta = -1$, item 2: $\beta = 1$)

One of the foremost advantages of IRT over CTT is that it allows us to assess measurement precision through the test information function (TIF), which is dependent not only on the discrimination of items, but also on the match between item difficulty

and the examinee's ability (Hambleton et al., 1991)³. A good measurement instrument within the IRT framework should therefore contain items of high discrimination⁴ and a mix of item difficulty if it is to reliably measure participants with a wide range of latent abilities. The amount of information a test provides at a certain level of latent trait is inversely related to the standard error of measurement: $SE(\theta) = 1 / \sqrt{I(\theta)}$. Thus, the more information a test provides, the fewer the errors associated with estimating the examinee's ability at that point, and the greater the reliability of the estimate, which can be expressed as: $r = 1 - (1/I)$ (Primi et al., 2015, p. 454).

Summary and goals of the present investigation

To summarise, in this study I present an item response theory analysis of Toplak's et al. (2014) Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test. The data were collected from a large sample of university students who completed the CRT7 and provided self-reported information about their preferred cognitive styles, which was measured by the Preference for Intuition and Deliberation Scale (PID, Betsch, 2008). This scale was used to assess the convergent validity of the CRT7 with the self-reported measure of thinking dispositions, as well as to ascertain whether the CRT7 shows the same pattern of correlations with an intuitive and deliberative cognitive style as does the original CRT3.

While to my knowledge there has been no study examining the correlations

³ This is important because in the CTT the reliability of the measurement is a property of the test as a whole, and it is assumed that there is no variation at different levels of latent ability, even though this assumption is often thought to be unrealistic (Hambleton et al., 1991).

⁴ According to Baker (2001), the item discrimination values can be interpreted thus: $\alpha < .64$ as low, $\alpha = .65 - 1.34$ as moderate, $\alpha = 1.35 - 1.69$ as high, and $\alpha > 1.70$ as very high discrimination

between the PID and the CRT, previous research has revealed a strong relationship between the PID subscales and the subscales of the Rational-Experiential Inventory (Witteman, Bercken, Claes, & Godoy, 2009), which have been repeatedly shown to correlate with the CRT (e.g. Pennycook, Cheyne et al., 2015; but see Erceg & Bubić, 2017). The PID was chosen for the present study primarily because its subscales are shorter than the more commonly employed scales of the Rational-Experiential Inventory, and because the latter have been shown to include items which Slovak participants have difficulty understanding (Ballová Mikušková, Hanák, & Čavojová, 2015), and our research sample consisted of Slovaks.

Crucially for the present investigation, I fitted the 2PL parametric item response theory model to estimate item difficulty and the discrimination parameters, as well as the test information function of CRT7. The original CRT3 was compared with the extended CRT7 across the analyses to assess whether it constituted an adequate expansion of Frederick's (2005) original three-item test. I also conducted several commonly used psychometric analyses, which can be directly compared to Toplak's et al. (2014) results concerning the CRT7.

METHOD

Participants

A total of 1,648 Slovak students participated in an online study that comprised seven CRT items and a self-report PID scale. The participants were recruited on a voluntary basis through a link which was shared on the online sites of every major Slovak university and college. The participants were studying for various majors, most typically economics and management (20.8%), engineering (14.9%), social science (12.5%), and pedagogy (10.8%). Of the total 1,648 participants, 444 (27%) reported

being familiar with at least one item in the original CRT. These participants achieved higher accuracy on the CRT3 ($M = 2.09$, $SD = 1.04$), than those unfamiliar with the original items ($M = 1.30$, $SD = 1.17$), $t(884.1) = 13.206$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.69$.

Interestingly, they also obtained higher scores on the CRT4 ($M = 2.71$, $SD = 1.23$) in comparison with the rest of the sample ($M = 2.12$, $SD = 1.38$), $t(883) = 8.336$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.44$; although the effect of the difference was smaller in this case. Consequently, these participants were excluded from subsequent analyses to avoid contaminating the results (see Haigh, 2016)⁵. This resulted in a final sample of 1,204 participants (812 female, 392 male, age: $M = 21.66$, $SD = 2.00$).

Materials and procedure

The participants were first asked to complete the *Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test*, which comprised three original items developed by Frederick (2005) as well as four new items reported in Toplak et al. (2014). The problems were open ended, with the exception of the last item, where participants had to choose from three response options. The exact wording of the whole test was as follows (taken from Toplak et al., 2014, p. 153):

1. A bat and a ball cost \$1.10 in total. The bat costs a dollar more than the ball. How much does the ball cost? ____ cents.
2. If it takes 5 machines 5 minutes to make 5 widgets, how long would it take 100 machines to make 100 widgets? ____ minutes.

⁵ However, as there is now evidence that exposure might not negatively affect the CRT (Bialek & Pennycook, 2017), an identical IRT analysis was also repeated on the CRT7 using the full sample ($N = 1648$, including participants familiar with the CRT). The results are in accord with the conclusions presented in the main article (see Supplementary material), with the exception of the difficulty estimates of the individual items, which are lower, as on average the participants in the full sample found the CRT7 items easier to solve.

3. In a lake, there is a patch of lily pads. Every day, the patch doubles in size. If it takes 48 days for the patch to cover the entire lake, how long would it take for the patch to cover half of the lake? _____ days.

4. If John can drink one barrel of water in 6 days, and Mary can drink one barrel of water in 12 days, how long would it take them to drink one barrel of water together? _____ days.

5. Jerry received both the 15th highest and the 15th lowest mark in the class. How many students are in the class? _____ students.

6. A man buys a pig for \$60, sells it for \$70, buys it back for \$80, and sells it finally for \$90. How much has he made? _____ dollars.

7. Simon decided to invest \$8,000 in the stock market one day early in 2008. Six months after he invested, on July 17, the stocks he had purchased were down 50%. Fortunately for Simon, from July 17 to October 17, the stocks he had purchased went up 75%. At this point, Simon has: a. broken even in the stock market, b. is ahead of where he began, c. has lost money.

The responses to the CRT problems were first categorised as correct, intuitively incorrect, or “other” incorrect (see Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015), then for the main analyses, the answers were coded as either 0 = incorrect or 1 = correct. Concerning reliability, the CRT3, CRT4, and CRT7 all had satisfactory values of Cronbach’s α of .70, .65, and .79, respectively. It is worth noting that the removal of one of the problems (the pig item) resulted in a slight increase in internal consistency for the remaining six items ($\alpha = .80$).

After completing the CRT7, the participants were presented with a self-report *Preference for Intuition and Deliberation Scale* (Betsch, 2008). The scale consisted of 18 items divided into two subscales: Preference for Intuition (PID-I) and Preference for Deliberation (PID-D). The participants were asked to rate their agreement with statements such as “I don’t like situations that require me to rely on my intuition” (PID-I, reverse scored) and “Before making decisions I first think them through” (PID-D) on a 5-point scale. The mean scores for the present sample were $M = 3.24$ ($SD = 0.60$) for PID-I and $M = 3.60$ ($SD = 0.66$) for PID-D. Both subscales showed good internal consistency (PID-I: $\alpha = .74$; PID-D: $\alpha = .79$), in accordance with the values reported by Betsch (2008).

Item response theory analysis

There are three assumptions underlying most IRT models which were checked before fitting the 2PL model to the data: unidimensionality, local independence, and correct model specification (DeMars, 2010). For a unidimensional 2PL model to be used it is necessary to ensure that all the items tap into one common dimension, as the model estimates only one θ value for each examinee. Modified parallel analysis (Drasgow & Lissak, 1983) was conducted to evaluate the assumption of unidimensionality in the seven CRT items. Closely related to this, is the assumption of local independence, in which it is assumed participants' responses to the individual items should not be mutually correlated after conditioning on their latent ability (θ). The G^2 indices (Chen & Thissen, 1997) were calculated to evaluate local dependence (LD) among the items, and cut points of 3.84 and 6.63 corresponding to the threshold levels for statistical significance of $p = .05$ and $p = .01$ were used. Finally, if one wants to interpret the estimated item and test parameters, it is necessary to ensure that the selected model fits the data well. This was done by testing model and item fit. I evaluated the overall fit of the 2PL model using M_2 statistic (Maydeu-Olivares & Joe, 2006), as well as other common indices of model fit (RMSEA, TLI, CFI). The fit of each item in the 2PL model was assessed using $S\text{-}\chi^2$ statistic (Orlando & Thissen, 2000, 2003). As this index can produce inflated type I error rates for short tests (DeMars, 2010), a more conservative threshold of $p < .01$ was employed to test for a possible misfit.

Having checked these assumptions, I fitted a 2PL model to the data. The parameters were estimated using unconditional maximum likelihood estimation with an EM algorithm (Bock & Aitkin, 1981). All the analyses were conducted using R 3.3.1 software (R Core Team, 2016). The IRT procedures were employed in the *mirt* package

(Chalmers, 2012), with the exception of modified parallel analysis, which was conducted using *ltm* (Rizopoulos, 2006).

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics and inter-item correlations

The descriptive statistics for the seven CRT items are shown in Table 1. As can be seen from the first column, most of the participants' responses to each item could be categorised as either correct or intuitive incorrect responses. However, as was the case in the study by Toplak et al. (2014), the proportions of "other" incorrect responses were higher for the four new problems than they were for the CRT3. The mean performance was 43.5% ($SD = 39.1\%$), 53.0% ($SD = 34.5\%$), and 48.9% ($SD = 32.9\%$) items correct on the CRT3, CRT4, and CRT7, respectively. Importantly, while 58% and 37% of the participants in the present sample answered either none or all of the items correctly in the CRT3 and CRT4, respectively, only 22% gave either all or no correct answers in the CRT7. Thus, using the seven-item composite led to a substantial reduction in the ceiling and floor effects.

Next, following Toplak et al. (2014), I was interested in whether the four new problems could serve as an adequate supplement to the original CRT3. The results of these analyses were very promising. For one thing, as can be seen from the right-hand section of Table 1, all of the individual items were moderately correlated. The mean inter-item correlations were .43, .32, and .35 for the CRT3, CRT4, and CRT7,⁶

⁶ As is immediately obvious from the right-hand section of Table 1, the inter-item correlations were somewhat lower for the pig item than for the remaining problems. After removing this item from the analysis, the inter-item correlation among the remaining six problems increased substantially to .40.

respectively. For another, the scores in the CRT4 were highly correlated with the CRT3, $r(1204) = .62, p < .001$. In addition to their good reliability coefficients (see Methods section), these results suggest that the four new and the three original CRT problems could be combined to form a meaningful composite.

Table 1. Item descriptives and inter-item correlations

<i>Item descriptives</i>			<i>Item correlations</i>						
Item	Correct	Intuitive incorrect	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Bat and ball	41 %	56 %	1						
2. Widgets	44 %	50 %	.39	1					
3. Lily pads	45 %	41 %	.44	.47	1				
4. Barrel	50 %	23 %	.36	.39	.48	1			
5. Marks	46 %	27 %	.39	.38	.47	.44	1		
6. Pig	49 %	28 %	.20	.19	.22	.24	.28	1	
7. Stocks	67 %	27 %	.33	.31	.40	.39	.39	.20	1

Note. Descriptives contain the percentages of correct and intuitive incorrect responses to the items. Correlations are based on 1204 observations. All correlations are significant at $p < .001$

Gender differences

As in past research (Frederick, 2005), I found considerable gender differences in performance on the original CRT3, with men scoring higher ($M = 1.72, SD = 1.13$) than women ($M = 1.10, SD = 1.14$), $t(782.3) = 8.901, p < .001, d = 0.55$. Similar results were obtained on the CRT4, where men ($M = 2.59, SD = 1.25$) also outperformed women ($M = 1.89, SD = 1.38$), $t(849.3) = 8.800, p < .001, d = 0.52$. The observed effect size is similar in magnitude to the gender differences reported for both composites by Toplak et al. (2014).

Cognitive reflection and Preference for intuition and deliberation

Concerning the convergent measures of the intuitive and reflective thinking styles, I

analysed correlations between the two subscales of the PID and the three CRT composites. As expected, the CRT3 showed negative correlation with PID-I, $r(1204) = -.13, p < .001$. The same was true for the CRT4 and CRT7 ($r_s = -.13$ and $-.15$, respectively, both $p_s < .001$). Also in line with my expectations, the PID-D correlated positively with the CRT3, $r(1204) = .14, p < .001$, as well as the CRT4 and CRT7 ($r_s = .16$ and $.17$, respectively, both $p_s < .001$). Thus, the four new items, as well as the seven-item composite, showed relationships with self-report measures of a preference for intuition and deliberation which were similar to those of the original CRT3. However, it should be mentioned that while the correlations were in the predicted direction, they were very low. I offer several possible reasons for this in the discussion.

Item response theory analysis

As a first step in fitting the 2PL model to the data, I evaluated the assumptions of the IRT analysis. Supporting the assumption of unidimensionality, the modified parallel analysis showed that the second eigenvalue in the observed data (.486) was not significantly larger than the average second eigenvalue of the data generated under a 2PL model (.485) in the 500 Monte Carlo samples, $p = .471$. As can be seen from Table 2, all the items load highly onto the same factor, although the loading of the pig problem is considerably smaller in comparison with the other items. Next, I checked for substantial residual covariance among the items that could not be accounted for by the unidimensional 2PL model. None of the G^2 indices for the item pairs exceeded critical thresholds, with the largest value being observed between the marks and the pig item, $G^2(1) = 3.53, p = .06$. Thus, it was concluded that the items are locally independent. Finally, I evaluated the fit of the 2PL model to the data. The results showed that the overall model fitted the data very well, $M_2(14) = 21.311, p = .09$, RMSEA = .021, TLI = .996, CFI = .997. Concerning the fit of the individual items under the 2PL curve,

while the $S\text{-}\chi^2$ statistics for each item were non-significant (Table 2), the lily pads problem showed the highest $S\text{-}\chi^2$ value, indicating a possible misfit. To further assess this issue, I examined the empirical plot of the observed and model expected scores for this item (DeMars, 2010). A visual inspection suggested the item fitted the model reasonably well, thus no further action was taken.

Table 2. Item fit indices, factor loadings, and IRT item parameters for the seven items of the CRT7

Item	$S\text{-}\chi^2$ (df)	λ	α (SE)	β (SE)
Bat and ball	7.36 (4)	.73	1.83 (.15)	.32 (.05)
Widgets	2.87 (4)	.74	1.86 (.15)	.20 (.05)
Lily pads	11.34 (4)	.86	2.92 (.26)	.15 (.04)
Barrel	0.63 (4)	.78	2.14 (.17)	.02 (.05)
Marks	5.75 (4)	.79	2.21 (.18)	.13 (.05)
Pig	2.22 (4)	.42	.80 (.08)	.04 (.08)
Stocks	0.53 (4)	.73	1.79 (.15)	-.60 (.06)

Note. Numbers in parentheses indicate standard errors (SE) or, in the case of $S\text{-}\chi^2$ indices, degrees of freedom (df). Item difficulty parameters were converted using the *equatedIRT* package (Battauz, 2015) from intercept parameters provided by *mirt*. Column labeled λ shows IRT parameters transformed into standardised factor loadings. Item fit indices ($S\text{-}\chi^2$) are all non-significant at $p = .01$

The item parameters estimated under the 2PL model are presented in Table 2. Concerning item difficulty, the β parameters range from $-.60$ (stocks) to $.32$ (bat and ball). As is apparent from Figure 2, most of the items are located slightly above the medium level of the latent ability continuum, signalling the range within which they function best. As for the discrimination parameters (α), all the items had very high discrimination levels according to Baker's (2001) benchmarks (α values > 1.7), except for the pig problem ($\alpha = 0.80$), which could be categorised as moderately discriminating. This is again evident from Figure 2, as the item characteristic curves for other items are much steeper than the curve of the pig item. Altogether, the results of the item-level analysis suggest that while each of the six remaining problems works

very well in itself, meaning they are good at discriminating between participants with different levels of cognitive reflection trait, these problems are quite similar in terms of difficulty. Therefore, participants who are located, for instance, one standard deviation below the mean level of the cognitive reflection trait ($\theta = -1$) have quite a low probability of answering any of the problems correctly, and vice versa, participants with above average cognitive reflection ($\theta = 1$) are very likely to answer most of the items correctly.

Figure 2. Item characteristic curves of the seven items in the CRT7 under the two-parameter logistic model. The x-axis represents a latent ability (θ) and the y-axis represents the probability of a correct response to an item

The item parameters determine how much information the item provides about examinees with different levels of latent trait. The information functions of the individual items can be summed to create a test information function which serves as an indicator of the reliability of an instrument. In order to compare the measurement precision of the original and the extended CRT, I first calculated the TIF only for the

first three items which comprise the CRT3. As could be expected on the basis of item difficulty, the measurement precision of the CRT3 is highest in the range slightly above the medium level of latent trait, around $\theta = 0.2$ ($I = 3.81, r = .74$). However, the estimates are reliable between latent trait levels of $\theta = -0.2$ ($I = 3.08, r = .68$) and $\theta = 0.5$ ($I = 3.28, r = .70$), even though they drop drastically in the lower and upper levels of latent trait⁷.

Concerning the test information function of all seven items, the highest measurement precision of the CRT7 is also near the mean levels of latent trait, around $\theta = 0.1$ ($I = 6.85, r = .85$). But, as can be seen from Figure 3, the information function for the CRT7 is high in a wider range of latent trait. Sufficiently reliable estimates are provided between $\theta = -0.8$ ($I = 3.20, r = .69$) and $\theta = 1$ ($I = 3.00, r = .67$), but these values drop below $I = 3$ (corresponding to the level of reliability $< .67$) under and over the aforementioned levels of latent ability⁸. The TIF of the CRT7 shows that the information we gain about participants using this instrument is very high but this is only true for participants with average levels of cognitive reflection. Measurement precision drops substantially in participants whose cognitive reflection trait is below or above average, as the test does not contain items with difficulties located at the lower and higher ends of the trait continuum. Nevertheless, while the measurement precision of both the CRT3 and CRT7 is quite high at medium levels of latent ability, the seven-item

⁷ Note that these results are quite similar to the reliability estimates of the original CRT presented in Primi et al. (2015).

⁸ In line with previous analyses, I calculated the TIF for the whole test after excluding the pig item. The results showed that this item did not contribute much to the measurement precision of the instrument, and its removal did not lead to a large decrease in the information provided at levels of latent trait of between $\theta = -0.8$ ($I = 3.05, r = .67$) and $\theta = 1$ ($I = 2.87, r = .65$).

test provides much more information about examinees lower or higher in the cognitive reflection trait than does the original CRT3⁹.

⁹ For completeness, the TIF for the CRT4 was also calculated. While similarly to the other two versions of the test, the highest measurement precision of the CRT4 was around the mean level of latent trait $\theta = 0.0$ ($I = 3.11$, $r = .68$), the range of its reliable estimates was quite narrow, between $\theta = -0.2$ ($I = 3.02$, $r = .67$) and $\theta = 0.2$ ($I = 2.98$, $r = .66$).

Figure 3. Test information function of CRT7 under two-parameter logistic model. Solid line represents amount of information at certain level of latent ability (θ), while the dashed line represents the standard error of an estimate

DISCUSSION

The present study examined the psychometric properties of the Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test proposed by Toplak et al. (2014). In line with the results they provided, I have found CRT7 to be an adequate extension of the original test. This is supported by the high correlation between the original and the newly constructed items (.62), a mean inter-item correlation of .35, and good reliability of the CRT7 ($\alpha = .79$). As in Toplak et al. (2014), both the original and the new items showed similar patterns of gender

differences. Finally, while the dimensionality of the CRT7 was not explicitly examined by Toplak et al. (2014), the present study shows that the four new items share a single-factor structure with the original CRT3. These results, obtained from a substantially larger sample than the one used in Toplak et al. (2014), provide corroborating evidence for the adequacy of the CRT7.

The dimensionality of the original test is rarely studied (Primi et al., 2015) and that of the CRT7 has not previously been examined to my knowledge, but both seem to reflect a single latent construct. While the factor loading of the pig problem was not very high, all the items satisfied the assumptions of the unidimensional IRT analysis and showed good fit in the 2PL model with a single latent trait. This is in line with the results of Primi et al. (2015), who similarly showed that one latent construct is responsible for responses on their novel version of the CRT; however, it runs counter to recent evidence presented by Stuppel et al. (2017) who, based on their chronometric analyses, question the unidimensionality of the CRT3. While the present study cannot tell us anything about their reaction time analyses, from the psychometric perspective the items in both the CRT3 and the CRT7 seem to measure one construct. However, it would certainly be interesting to examine this point further by employing the chronometric analyses presented by Stuppel et al. (2017) to examine the characteristics of the extended versions of the CRT.

Beyond the traditional psychometric analyses, I fitted a 2PL model to the seven items in order to examine their difficulty and discrimination parameters within an IRT framework. As was shown in Table 2, most of the items differentiate between participants with different levels of cognitive reflection trait very well. However, while one item was located along the lower levels of the latent trait continuum ($\beta = -.60$), all the remaining problems had relatively similar difficulty parameters, ranging only from

.02 to .32. Accordingly, the inspection of the TIF showed that particularly high standard errors should be expected when the test is administered to examinees with below-average levels of cognitive reflection trait. Still, in comparison with the CRT3, which is only capable of reliably differentiating among examinees with a very restricted range of cognitive reflection (see also Primi et al., 2015), the CRT7 provides much greater measurement precision along a wider range of the latent trait continuum.

While overall the results suggest that the problems developed by Toplak et al. (2014) can be readily used in future research, one of the items emerged as consistently problematic across the item-level analyses conducted in the present study. The pig problem had low correlations with other items, and its removal led to an increase in inter-item correlations and the overall reliability of the remaining six problems. Furthermore, it showed a low discrimination ability, and consequently, in addition to being located around the mean levels of latent trait along with most other items, it did not contribute much information to the TIF. It is disputable whether the meagre additional information this item provides outweighs the costs of having a longer test. Thus, in future use of the CRT7, researchers are advised to consider excluding the pig item from the test altogether, or at least to be aware of the aforementioned problems that may result from its use.

As predicted, based on studies showing that the CRT correlates with other measures of favouring intuitive and analytic thinking, such as Faith in Intuition (FI) and Need for Cognition scales (NFC; e.g. Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015), I found the CRT correlates positively with the PID-D and negatively with the PID-I subscales of the self-report PID questionnaire. However, it is worth noting that while this is highly significant and in the expected direction, the correlations between self-report thinking style and the CRT in the present study were very low in magnitude. One reasons for the

low correlations could be that in this study the PID questionnaire was used instead of the more commonly employed NFC and FI. The PID questionnaire may capture slightly different aspects of the preference for intuitive and deliberative thinking than the NFC and the FI (Betsch, 2008). However, empirical studies show that the PID subscales are strongly related to the NFC and FI (Ballová Mikušková et al., 2015; Witteman et al., 2009). Therefore, it does not seem likely that the low correlations observed in the present study could have resulted solely because of the differences between the PID and more commonly employed scales for measuring thinking dispositions.

Another possible reason for the low correlations is that the CRT may simply not be a reliable measure of analytic and intuitive thinking dispositions, reflecting other constructs that have been implicated in solving the CRT instead, such as rational thinking and numerical ability (e.g. Campitelli & Gerrans, 2014). This conclusion is supported by other researchers who have observed similarly weak relationships among the CRT, FI and NFC (Alós-Ferrer & Hügelschäfer, 2014; Frederick, 2005). Importantly, in their recent studies, Erceg and Bubić (2017) have also observed very low correlations between the subscales of the Rational-Experiential Inventory and the CRT and have concluded that either thinking dispositions do not play a strong role in performance in the CRT, or that the relationship between the two could be dependent on specific aspects of the research sample, such as education domain. For example, in one of their studies, the relationship between the NFC and CRT was significant in humanities and social science students, but not among science and engineering students. While the present research did not investigate this issue directly, it should be noted that the low correlations reported here were obtained from a very large sample consisting of students taking different majors and the results are similar to the conclusions of Erceg

and Bubić (2017) that thinking dispositions seem to be only very weakly related to performance on the CRT.

As was mentioned in the introduction, one of the problems with measuring cognitive reflection is that potential participants may be familiar with (some of) the items in the original CRT3. In the present investigation I strived to avoid pools of participants where familiarity is known to be particularly problematic, such as MTurk participants, or psychology students (Haigh, 2016; Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016). Despite my efforts, 27% of the present sample reported being familiar with at least one item in the CRT3. As in previous studies (Haigh, 2016; Pennycook, Cheyne, et al., 2015), these participants gave more correct responses to the CRT3 than did the naive participants ($d = 0.69$). Furthermore, they also showed greater accuracy on items in the CRT4, with which they were unlikely to be familiar,¹⁰ though the effect size of the difference was smaller in this case ($d = 0.44$). Presumably, people familiar with the original problems were aware that these are trick questions and were subsequently more cautious in approaching other items too. If this is the case, then including the CRT3, even if only as a part of the longer newly developed tests (e.g. CRT-L, Primi et al., 2015; CRT7, Toplak et al., 2014) may lead to higher percentages of correct responses on the whole method.

However, as a recent study by Bialek and Pennycook (2017) suggests, while previous exposure to the CRT may lead to increased scores on the test, it might not affect the CRT's predictive validity. In the present study, it was possible to compare the results of the IRT analysis of the CRT7 in the sample including and excluding

¹⁰ While I did not ask participants whether they were familiar with any of the CRT4 items, I doubt this was the case, as the research was performed shortly after publication by Toplak et al. (2014).

participants with previous familiarity of the original test (see Supplementary Materials). The convergence of the two analyses seems to further support the conclusions of Bialek and Pennycook (2017), that while participants exposed to some items tend to score better on the CRT, making the items less difficult, in other respects the test seems to retain its psychometric characteristics even when the exposed participants are included in the sample.

While, to my knowledge this study presents the first IRT analysis of the extended version of the CRT developed by Toplak et al. (2014), recently Primi et al. (2015) have applied IRT methods to develop and test their own new CRT problems. Importantly in relation to the present investigation, they mention several limitations with the CRT7, which I would like to briefly address here. Primi et al. (2015) were specifically concerned about the forced choice format of the stocks item, the high proportion of non-intuitive incorrect responses to the barrel problem, the questionable dimensionality of the test, and the size of the sample on which its development was based. I believe that the present results, obtained from a much larger sample of participants than that used by Toplak et al. (2014), counter most of these problems. First of all, the stocks item showed good discrimination and, while the forced choice format may have resulted in this problem being less difficult, this is in fact beneficial, as the item can thus function better among participants with lower cognitive reflection. Next, although the proportion of non-intuitive incorrect responses on the barrel item was slightly higher than that of intuitive incorrect responses, 73% of the participants in the present sample produced either an intuitively incorrect or the correct response. This proportion seems reasonably high, considering that it is very hard to create new problems that elicit such compelling intuitive errors as did the original CRT3. Finally, I

believe that the results show substantial evidence in favour of the unidimensionality of the CRT7.

Regarding the study by Primi et al. (2015) and the present research, I would now like to discuss the implications of the two IRT analyses for further developments in measuring cognitive reflection. Both the CRT7 discussed here and the CRT-L developed by Primi et al. (2015) have proved to be valuable extensions of the original test. They show good internal consistency, a high discrimination of individual items, and a substantial reduction in the floor effects that were problematic in the CRT3. Moreover, the two extensions exhibited relationships with reasoning and decision making tasks, general intelligence, numeracy, and thinking dispositions, which are similar to those of the original three-item method (Primi et al., 2015; Toplak et al., 2014). Despite the advantages that the CRT7 and CRT-L offer, there is still potential for further development in the field of measuring cognitive reflection. For example, both the extensions are somewhat restricted in the range of item difficulty. Most items in the present study, as well as in Primi et al. (2015), have very similar difficulty parameters, which span a limited range of the above-medium levels of latent trait. Consequently, analyses of the TIFs have shown that both the CRT7 and CRT-L provide most information around a relatively narrow range (approximately 1 SD) around the medium level of the latent trait, but their measurement precision drops substantially below and above this range.

These results point to a further need to develop new CRT items of various difficulties that measure a wider range of cognitive reflection trait. In fact, many new problems are already available (Baron et al., 2015; Oldrati et al., 2016; Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016), but their psychometric qualities have not yet been extensively studied. To address this issue, I believe it would be beneficial to summarise all the

existing CRT items and to conduct a large psychometric study to ascertain whether they are indeed adequate for measuring cognitive reflection. Such an endeavour could result in the creation of a large bank of items that would be readily available as a substitute for the original CRT3. Importantly, creating a wider item bank with known IRT parameters would enable use of one of the most important applications of IRT – computerised adaptive testing (CAT; Embretson & Reise, 2000; Hambleton et al., 1991). In CAT, the examinees are presented with items that are selected so as to be maximally informative about their estimated ability level, based on their previous responses. For example, participants who fail to answer easier items at the start of the test are subsequently not presented with the most difficult questions, which are judged to be too demanding for their estimated level of latent ability. One of the advantages of CAT is that it offers a more accurate estimate of ability and fewer items are administered (Embretson & Reise, 2000; Hambleton et al., 1991). This is crucial for assessing cognitive reflection, as administering all the available items to all participants would quickly lead to familiarity issues, in much the same way as occurred with the CRT3. Similarly, presenting a long row of CRT items might also raise the participant’s suspicion about the tricky nature of the problems, which may lead to increased caution and subsequent checking and correcting of previous responses (Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016). For these reasons I believe that having a broad item bank available for CAT would prove particularly advantageous for further developments in the field of cognitive reflection measurement.

Conclusion

To summarise, the present article offers a comprehensive psychometric analysis of the Expanded Cognitive Reflection Test developed by Toplak et al. (2014). The results show that the CRT7 seems to be an adequate extension to the original CRT3, as evidenced by the high correlation between the original and newly designed items,

satisfactory reliability, the unidimensional structure of the CRT7, and similar patterns of gender differences and correlations with self-report measures of thinking styles between the original and extended version of the CRT. However, the present analyses suggested that the pig item does not fit well with the remaining problems, and its removal from the CRT7 should be considered in future research. Furthermore, the present investigation underlines the need for new CRT items, both ones that are unfamiliar to the general public, and ones varying in difficulty, so that a wide range of cognitive reflection trait can be measured. To help develop a broader item bank of CRT problems, researchers could take advantage of the many items that have been proposed in recently published work (Baron et al., 2015; Oldrati et al., 2016; Thomson & Oppenheimer, 2016). This could lead both to computerised adaptive testing of the cognitive reflection trait, and to the construction of parallel forms of the CRT, comprised of problems with a wide range of item difficulty. While such an endeavour would require the further development of a large amount of CRT items with adequate psychometric properties, I believe that if successful, it would constitute a much appreciated solution to problems facing researchers interested in cognitive reflection measurement.

REFERENCES

- Alós-Ferrer, C., & Hügelschäfer, S. (2014). Faith in intuition and cognitive reflection. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 64, 61–70.
- Baker, F. B. (2001). *The Basics of Item Response Theory* (2nd ed.). ERIC Clearinghouse on Assessment and Evaluation. DOI:10.1111/j.1365-2362.2010.02362.x
- Ballová Mikušková, E., Hanák, R., & Čavojová, V. (2015). Appropriateness of two inventories measuring intuition (The PID and the REI) for Slovak population. *Studia Psychologica*, 57(1), 63–82.

- Baron, J., Scott, S., Fincher, K., & Emlen Metz, S. (2015). Why does the cognitive reflection test (sometimes) predict utilitarian moral judgment (and other things)? *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 4(3), 265–284.
- Battauz, M. (2015). equateIRT: An R package for IRT test equating. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 68(7), 1–22.
- Betsch, C. (2008). Chronic preferences for intuition and deliberation in decision making: Lessons learned about intuition from an individual differences approach. In H. Plessner, C. Betsch, & T. Betsch (Eds.), *Intuition in Judgment and Decision Making* (pp. 231–248). London, UK: Taylor & Francis.
- Bialek, M., & Pennycook, G. (2017). The cognitive reflection test is robust to multiple exposures. *Behavior Research Methods*, 1–7.
- Bock, R. D., & Aitkin, M. (1981). Marginal maximum likelihood estimation of item parameters: Application of an EM algorithm. *Psychometrika*, 46(4), 443–459.
- Campitelli, G., & Gerrans, P. (2014). Does the cognitive reflection test measure cognitive reflection? A mathematical modeling approach. *Memory & Cognition*, 42(3), 434–447.
- Calvillo, D. P., & Burgeno, J. N. (2015). Cognitive reflection predicts the acceptance of unfair ultimatum game offers. *Judgment and Decision Making*, 10(4), 332–341.
- de Ayala, R. J. (2009). *The theory and practice of item response theory*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- DeMars, C. (2010). *Item response theory*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Dragow, F., & Lissak, R. I. (1983). Modified parallel analysis: A procedure for examining the latent dimensionality of dichotomously scored item responses. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 68(3), 363–373.
- Embretson, S. E., & Reise, S. P. (2000). *Item response theory for psychologists*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Erceg, N., & Bubić, A. (2017). One test, five scoring procedures: different ways of approaching the cognitive reflection test. *Journal of Cognitive Psychology*, 29(3), 381–392.
- Frederick, S. (2005). Cognitive reflection and decision making. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 19(4), 25–42.
- Haigh, M. (2016). Has the standard cognitive reflection test become a victim of its own success? *Advances in Cognitive Psychology*, 12(3), 145–149.

- Hambleton, R. K., Swaminathan, H., & Rogers, D. J. (1991). *Fundamentals of item response theory*. London, UK: Sage Publications.
- Chalmers, R. P. (2012). mirt: A multidimensional item response theory package for the R environment. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 48(6), 1–29.
- Chen, W.-H., & Thissen, D. (1997). Local dependence indexes for item pairs using item response theory. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, 22(3), 265–289.
- Jackson, S. A., Kleitman, S., Howie, P., & Stankov, L. (2016). Cognitive abilities, monitoring confidence, and control thresholds explain individual differences in heuristics and biases. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7(October), 1559.
- Maydeu-Olivares, A., & Joe, H. (2006). Limited information goodness-of-fit testing in multidimensional contingency tables. *Psychometrika*, 71(4), 713–732.
- Oldrati, V., Patricelli, J., Colombo, B., & Antonietti, A. (2016). The role of dorsolateral prefrontal cortex in inhibition mechanism: A study on cognitive reflection test and similar tasks through neuromodulation. *Neuropsychologia*, 91, 499–508.
- Orlando, M., & Thissen, D. (2000). Likelihood-based item-fit indices for dichotomous item response theory models. *Applied Psychological Measurement*, 24(1), 50–64.
- Orlando, M., & Thissen, D. (2003). Further investigation of the performance of S-X2: An item fit index for use with dichotomous item response theory models. *Applied Psychological Measurement*, 27(4), 289–298.
- Pennycook, G., Fugelsang, J. a., & Koehler, D. J. (2015). Everyday consequences of analytic thinking. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 24(6), 425–432.
- Pennycook, G., Cheyne, J. A., Koehler, D. J., & Fugelsang, J. a. (2015). Is the cognitive reflection test a measure of both reflection and intuition? *Behavior Research Methods*, 48, 341–348.
- Pennycook, G., & Ross, R. M. (2016). Commentary: Cognitive reflection vs. calculation in decision making. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 9.
- Primi, C., Morsanyi, K., Chiesi, F., Donati, M. A., & Hamilton, J. (2015). The development and testing of a new version of the cognitive reflection test applying item response theory (IRT). *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 29(5), 453–469.

- R Core Team. (2016). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Retrieved from <http://www.r-project.org/>
- Rizopoulos, D. (2006). ltm: An R package for latent variable modeling and item response theory analyses. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *17*(5), 1–25.
- Sinayev, A., & Peters, E. (2015). Cognitive reflection vs. calculation in decision making. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *6*(May), 1–16.
- Stupple, E. J. N., Pitchford, M., Ball, L. J., Hunt, T. E., & Steel, R. (2017). Slower is not always better: Response-time evidence clarifies the limited role of miserly information processing in the Cognitive Reflection Test. *PLoS ONE*, *12*(11), 1–18.
- Thomson, K. S., & Oppenheimer, D. M. (2016). Investigating an alternate form of the cognitive reflection test. *Judgment and Decision Making*, *11*(1), 99–113.
- Toplak, M. E., West, R. F., & Stanovich, K. E. (2011). The cognitive reflection test as a predictor of performance on heuristics-and-biases tasks. *Memory & Cognition*, *39*(7), 1275–1289.
- Toplak, M. E., West, R. F., & Stanovich, K. E. (2014). Assessing miserly information processing: An expansion of the cognitive reflection test. *Thinking & Reasoning*, *20*(2), 147–168.
- Witteman, C., Bercken, J. Van Den, Claes, L., & Godoy, A. (2009). Assessing Rational and Intuitive Thinking Styles. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment* *25*(1), 39–47.

